

**THE PRESIDENT SIGNED THE LAW "ON CONFLICT OF INTEREST"
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Head of the Legal Information Department
of the Jizzakh Regional Justice Department

Sh. Sulaymonov

Annotation: The law applies to state bodies and local government bodies, state institutions, state unitary enterprises, state trust funds, as well as joint-stock companies in whose authorized capital (authorized capital) the state share is 50 percent or more. The law introduces such basic concepts as an employee of a state body or other organization, conflict of interest, a special unit for regulating conflicts of interest, personal interest, close relatives.

Keywords: Employee of the organization, conflict of interest, the law refers to state bodies, enterprises.

The following persons are recognized as persons related to an employee of a state body or other organization:

Close relatives of an employee of a state body or other organization;

A legal entity in which an employee of a state body or other organization and (or) his/her close relatives own shares or interests in the authorized fund (authorized capital);

A legal entity in which an employee of a state body or other organization or his/her close relatives are the head or member of the management body.

The Anti-Corruption Agency is a specially authorized state body in the field of regulating relations related to conflicts of interest.

Control over compliance with the requirements of the law by an employee of a state body or other organization is carried out by an ethics commission established in this state body or other organization.

Disclosure of information on conflicts of interest is carried out by submitting a notification on existing conflicts of interest and a declaration on potential conflicts of interest by an employee of a state body or other organization.

The declaration of potential conflicts of interest must include the following information:

The position of an employee of a state body or other organization and his/her surname, first name, patronymic, as well as his/her personal identification number;

The surname, first name, patronymic of close relatives of an employee of a state body or other organization, their personal identification number (if any), as well as their place of work and position;

The official name of a joint-stock company in which an employee of a state body or other organization or his/her close relatives are shareholders, and its taxpayer identification number;

The official name of a legal entity in which a close relative of an employee of a state body or other organization is a founder (participant), member of the management body, as well as its taxpayer identification number.

It is not allowed to disclose personal information of persons entrusted to employees participating in the regulation and identification of conflicts of interest or who became known to them in connection with the performance of their professional, service or labor duties.

The ethics commission of state bodies or other organizations shall adopt a semi-annual conclusion on existing or potential conflicts of interest and consider the adequacy (correctness) of the measures taken to regulate them.

The ethics commission of state bodies or other organizations shall analyze the identified conflicts of interest together with a special unit and shall conduct explanatory work among employees of the state body or other organization.

Decisions made or transactions concluded in the presence of a conflict of interest shall be deemed invalid in court.

An employee of a state body or other organization must fill out a notification of a conflict of interest in the established form within 1 business day from the moment he becomes aware of the conflict of interest and submit it to his immediate superior (head of the organization - senior manager) or a special unit in the following cases:

close relatives are employed directly under the employee (except for cases of employment in a position belonging to the political group of civil service positions) or persons related to him are involved in the employee's work on the basis of a civil law contract;

if he participates in making decisions on issues related to persons related to him;

if his close relative works as an official responsible for the direction of the inspection at the object (legal entity) being inspected, or if this object of inspection (legal entity) is a person related to him;

if he becomes aware of any other existing conflict of interest.

The head of a state body or other organization and the head of a special unit are responsible for regulating the conflict of interest.

The head of a structural unit of a state body or other organization is obliged to provide information to the special unit within 1 working day on the measures taken within his powers to regulate the existing conflict of interest.

The special unit submits information to the ethics commission within 3 working days to consider the issue of the adequacy (correctness) of the measures taken.

An employee of a state body or other organization must fill out a declaration on a potential conflict of interest in the event of changes in personal data and submit it to a special unit no later than January 15 of each year.

A candidate for employment in a state body or other organization, as well as an employee transferred to another job, must fill out and submit a declaration on a

potential conflict of interest in the established form.

The special unit:

summarizes and analyzes the annual declaration on a potential conflict of interest by February 15 of each year;

submits a proposal to the ethics commission by March 1 of each year to ensure the adequacy (correctness) of measures to regulate a potential conflict of interest;

submits a proposal to the immediate superior of the employee of a state body or other organization or to a higher-ranking head of a state body or other organization to take measures to regulate a potential conflict of interest, based on the conclusion adopted by the ethics commission.

When a candidate for a position as an employee of a state body or other organization is hired, or when an employee of a state body or other organization is transferred to another job, after submitting a declaration on a potential conflict of interest, the special unit shall carry out the above-mentioned work within 5 days.

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